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Research Article

Analyzing voting power in decentralized governance: Who controls DAOs?

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ABSTRACT

We empirically study the state of three prominent DAO governance systems on the Ethereum blockchain: Compound, Uniswap and Ethereum name service (ENS). In particular, we examine how the voting power is distributed in these systems. Using a comprehensive dataset of all governance token holders, delegates, proposals, and votes, we analyze who holds the voting power and how this power is being used to influence governance decisions. While we reveal that the majority of voting power is concentrated in the hands of a small number of addresses, we rarely observe these powerful entities overturning a vote by choosing a different outcome than that of the overall community and less influential voters.

1. Introduction

Individuals with conflicting interests need to make joint decisions frequently in many parts of society: in political elections, at party conventions, or at shareholder meetings. How can such communities govern themselves and reach joint decisions in the most effective and inclusive way? Research on this question goes back centuries. In 1884, Charles Dodgson (better known as Lewis Carroll, the author of *Alice's Adventures in Wonderland*) suggested a transitive voting system in which candidates can transfer received votes to other candidates [1,2]. Today, this concept is commonly referred to as *liquid democracy* and can be seen as a hybrid between direct and representative democracy. It has found practical use in politics with, for instance, Germany's Pirate Party using liquid democracy for internal voting [3,4]. Even more adaption and development in this area has, however, emanated from communities around popular blockchain-based projects. Many such communities and stakeholder groups have formed so-called decentralized autonomous organizations (DAOs) in order to govern their projects and make decisions about the project's future in a decentralized manner. Such decisions could concern changes to a protocol or the use of the treasury funds of a project. With DAOs becoming more and more influential, so do their governance systems: Some DAOs including Uniswap manage sizable treasuries of multiple billion USD.¹ Moreover, their governance decision can be highly influential: Uniswap's governance, for example,

somewhat controversially voted to create a lobbying group called the "DeFi Education Fund" and allocated \$20 million of treasury funds to it in July 2021.²

The novel designs of DAO governance systems and the large amount of power they hold make it compelling and relevant to study how these systems work and how decisions are reached. Who holds the voting power in these systems, and how do the actors influence the decisions? In this paper, we study three of the most prominent and influential governance systems on the Ethereum blockchain: Compound, Uniswap, and Ethereum name service (ENS). Compound, a decentralized lending protocol [5], is one of the first protocols to introduce a governance system and has served as a role model for many other projects [6]. For instance, Uniswap, the second governance we examine, has adapted Compound's governance contracts. Uniswap is the clear market leader among decentralized exchanges and one of the most-used applications in decentralized finance (DeFi). Besides governing the protocol, Uniswap's governance also controls a multibillion dollar treasury. Finally, we study ENS, which is a vital part of Ethereum infrastructure and boasts one of the largest voting communities. In order to facilitate voting in a decentralized and pseudonymous setting, DAOs typically issue governance tokens and distribute them among stakeholders. These tokens can initially be distributed in different ways: Uniswap, for instance, distributes its UNI tokens among the team, early investors and early users via an airdrop [7]. Later, the tokens are freely tradable, mak-

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¹ For up-to-date numbers, see <https://deepdao.io/organizations>.

² <https://app.uniswap.org/#/vote/1/1>.

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Fig. 1. A visualization of the delegation network of token holders (blue nodes) and delegates (red nodes) in Compound governance.

ing it possible to buy tokens and thereby voting power. In this sense, governance tokens have similarities with shares in companies that come with voting rights at shareholder meetings.

The governance tokens can then be used to vote on governance proposals: Each token counts as one vote. To vote, a simple form of liquid democracy [8] is used: To be able to vote, a token holder must delegate their tokens to a *delegate*. Delegates can then vote on proposals with the number of tokens delegated to them. A visualization of the network of delegations for Compound is shown in Fig. 1. Note that both holders and delegates are addresses on the blockchain. In particular, multiple addresses can be controlled by the same person or organization.

Most DAO governance processes, including the three we study, involve multiple steps, only the last of which takes place on the blockchain. For example, the Uniswap governance process first requires a temperature check and a consensus check, both of which are off-chain and require a certain threshold of yes-votes. Only when these two thresholds are reached is a proposal put to a vote on-chain. In this paper, we concentrate on the final on-chain votes where the actual decisions are made.

In this paper, we analyze how voting power is distributed and used in DAO governance systems. In the process, we evaluate how decentralized these systems actually are (as this is a major goal of blockchain-based applications). Furthermore, we examine the structure of the delegation networks and study the voting behavior of different types of delegates. Finally, we discuss why it is not always possible to determine the exact distribution of power since multiple addresses on the blockchain can be controlled by the same entity.

2. Related work

A first attempt at creating a DAO was made with “The DAO” in the early days of the Ethereum blockchain in the year 2016 [9]. However, due to a hack, The DAO never actually operated as intended. One of the first governance systems for a blockchain-based application was introduced by the stablecoin protocol MakerDAO in 2018 [10]. A case study of MakerDAO’s governance can be found in Ref. [11]. Since Compound set up its token voting governance system in early 2020 [6], many other projects have followed suit. Some early analyses of the systems, mainly focusing on the ownership distribution of governance tokens of DeFi protocols, have been carried out in Refs. [12–14]. (For an overview of DeFi, see, e.g., Refs. [15,16].) In a recent, more detailed study, Barbereau et al. considered the governance systems of nine DeFi protocols: Uniswap, Aave, MakerDAO, Compound, SushiSwap, Synthetix, Yearn Finance, Ox, and UMA [17]. In their work, they focused mainly on token

Table 1
Key figures of the dataset.

	Holders	Delegates	Proposals	Total votes
Compound	188.198	1.766	84	3.431
Uniswap	306.580	5.784	10	1.660
ENS	57.511	11.597	– ^a	–

^a Up until 1 March 2022, two proposals were voted on by ENS governance, however these were not part of our dataset.

distribution and voter turnout. The analysis in our paper goes deeper in multiple ways; we additionally examine voting behavior and delegation network structure.

Voting systems similar to those currently used by many DAOs have a long history of academic discussion. They are commonly referred to as *delegative democracy* [18] or *liquid democracy* [1,8]. The governance systems we study use slightly simpler versions of these concepts with a main difference being that they only allow for voting rights to be delegated once from a token holder to a delegate. In liquid democracy, it is often possible for a delegate to further (recursively) delegate the tokens they received to another delegate. The practical application of liquid democracy has been examined in a case study of the internal voting system of the German Pirate Party [3,4].

3. Overview of the dataset

We collect comprehensive data on the token holders, delegates, votes and proposals for the Compound, Uniswap and ENS governance systems from the Ethereum blockchain. The three DAOs were chosen for being among the most influential DAOs on Ethereum at the time of writing (besides MakerDAO, which is studied in Ref. [11]): While Compound’s governance model and contract have become a role model copied by many other DAOs, and Uniswap DAO governs the by far most prominent DeFi application with a multibillion-dollar treasury, ENS has one of the largest communities of governance token holders.

Table 1 provides an overview of the state of these governance systems as of 1 March 2022. The analysis encompasses a more than two-year period between Ethereum blocks 9.000.000 (25 November 2019) and 14.300.000 (1 March 2022). To gather the data, we use the indexing protocol, The Graph, which allows querying Ethereum blockchain data. Specifically, we utilize three subgraphs that index governance-related transactions of the three DAOs in question.³ Since more such subgraphs are being created and open-sourced, this allows for extending this approach to more DAOs in the future [19].

The delegation networks of the governance systems are visualized in Figs. 1 and 2 using the Python library NetworkX [20]. An edge between a holder (blue node) and a delegate (red node) indicates a delegation. The sizes of the nodes are proportional to the number of tokens held or represented (with a minimum size for small holders and delegates).

A clear difference between Compound and Uniswap on the one side and ENS on the other side is visible at first glance: For ENS, delegates tend to have numerous holders of similar size delegating to them. For Compound and Uniswap, on the other hand, many delegates receive most of their voting power from a single large token holder delegating to them. Note that in such cases, it is possible that the holder and delegate addresses are both controlled by the same entity (and that the delegate address was set up for voting purposes only). We investigate the differences between the governance systems in more detail in Section 5.

³ <https://thegraph.com/hosted-service/subgraph/arr00/compound-governance-2>, <https://thegraph.com/hosted-service/subgraph/arr00/uniswap-governance-v2>, <https://thegraph.com/hosted-service/subgraph/ianlapham/ens-governance>.

Fig. 2. Delegation networks: Blue nodes represent holders and red nodes represent delegates. The sizes of the nodes are proportional to the number of tokens held or represented. Each edge indicates a delegation.

Fig. 3. Distribution of voting rights among delegates: Delegates are sorted by size, and the width of each box indicates the share of votes delegated to them.

4. Distribution of voting power

In the following, we study who holds the power in the governance systems. We examine this in three steps: 1) How are voting rights distributed? 2) How frequently are voting rights executed? 3) How much do the executed votes influence the final governance decision?

4.1. Distribution of voting rights

As a first step, we examine how voting rights are distributed in the three governance systems. Fig. 3 shows the distribution of delegated tokens among delegates. The visualization clearly illustrates the concentration of voting rights among a relatively limited number of delegates. To precisely quantify this concentration, we consider two inequality measures: the Gini coefficient and the Nakamoto coefficient.

The Gini coefficient [21] is the most commonly used index to measure inequality and ranges from 0 (perfect equality) to 1 (maximum inequality). It measures the area between the Lorenz curve of a given distribution and the curve of perfect equality [21]. Fig. 4 displays the Lorenz curves of the distribution of voting rights among delegates. For the remainder of this section, we consider the distributions of tokens at block 14.300.000, which occurred on 1 March 2022.

The precise Gini values in Table 2 indicate that ENS’ token distribution is less unequal than that of Compound and Uniswap, which have Gini values around 0.99. Nonetheless, the values prove a high degree of inequality in the distribution of voting rights in all three cases. In particular, the inequality is higher than that in the general distribution of wealth in the world: The Gini coefficient of the wealth distribution in 2020 is estimated to be 0.850 in the US, 0.814 in Europe, and 0.704 in China [22].

Moreover, we also see that the distribution of tokens among delegates is slightly more equal than the distribution among token holders.

Table 2

Gini and Nakamoto coefficients of the token distributions among holders, delegates, and delegates who voted at least once. All the numbers are rounded to 3 digits after the decimal point.

	Compound	Uniswap	ENS
Gini Holders	0.998	0.996	0.977
Gini Delegates	0.987	0.995	0.908
Gini Delegates Voted	0.964	0.971	–
Nakamoto Delegates	8	11	18

Finally, considering only delegates who voted at least once gives a slightly more equal distribution once again.

The Nakamoto coefficient [23] is a measure of how decentralized a system is. Applied to our setting, it counts the minimum number of delegates that together hold more than 50% of the voting power. The Nakamoto coefficients (see Table 2) reveal extreme centralization in all three governance systems: In the case of Compound, only 8 delegates can dictate any governance action using their majority. For Uniswap, this number is 11; for ENS, it is 18.

Considering the Gini coefficient over time (Fig. 5(a)) reveals that the strong inequality in the voting power distributions has persisted for an extended time period and even seems to be rising. On the other hand, increasing Nakamoto coefficients (Fig. 5(b)) do indicate that the systems are becoming slightly more decentralized over time.

4.2. Governance participation

A second crucial aspect in analyzing voting power is how often delegates participate in voting, i.e., how often delegates use their voting power.

The upper plots in Fig. 6 show the fraction of the total supply of governance tokens which is delegated (the total supply is 10 million for Compound and 1 billion for Uniswap). Since delegating is a prerequisite for voting, this is the maximum amount of tokens that could have participated in governance at that time. Furthermore, the figures show how many delegated tokens were actually used to vote for each proposal (each dot represents a proposal).

Note that only about two-thirds of the total supply of COMP and UNI tokens circulated at the end of our observation period according to CoinMarketCap.⁴ The remaining tokens will come into circulation

⁴ <https://coinmarketcap.com/>.

Fig. 4. Lorenz curves of the voting power distributions among delegates.

Fig. 5. Gini and Nakamoto coefficients for delegates over time.

Fig. 6. Governance participation: The upper figures show the number of delegated tokens over time and how many of them were used to vote in each proposal. The lower figures plot the total number of delegates and how many of them voted.

in the future. As only circulating tokens are available for delegation, the delegation rate of about 20% for Uniswap translates into 30% of all circulating tokens. As a consequence, 15% of circulating governance tokens can currently take control of Uniswap’s governance. Note that circulating supply has increased over time, which could in part explain the increase in delegated tokens.

The figures show that, on average, in both governance systems less than 10% of total tokens (or 15% of circulating tokens) participate in votes on proposals. Hence, 7.5% of circulating tokens would have already sufficed to win an average vote in the past. On the other hand, it should be noted that more than half the delegated tokens regularly vote.

Fig. 7. Voting participation of delegates.

For comparison, participation in voting at shareholder meetings of traditional companies (which arguably share some similarities at least with Uniswap and Compound governance) is significantly higher: According to Ref. [24], the participation rate among shareholders of US companies is about 70%.

The lower plots in Fig. 6 show the total number of delegates and how many of them participated in each vote. We find that only a very small number of delegates actually participate in voting (note the logarithmic y-axis). This again shows how these governance systems are centralized. For Compound, the number has been falling and the average is currently around 20, while it has lately been less than 100 for Uniswap.

Finally, we consider how the participation rate of delegates depends on the number of delegated tokens they have received. Fig. 7 plots how often delegates vote against the number of tokens delegated to them. Each dot represents a delegate, and the dashed line represents the regression line. We observe that delegates with more tokens delegated to them tend to vote more often. A notable exception is the second largest Uniswap delegate, who has been delegated almost 12.8 million UNI tokens (from a single address) worth more than \$13 million on 1 March 2022, but has never voted in a governance decision.

4.3. Potential and exercised voting power

As the final step, we examine how the votes that are cast actually influence the outcome of the governance decisions. It is one thing for delegates to have the possibility to change votes. A completely different matter is whether they actually choose to do so. To measure this, we use the following two metrics inspired by Kling et al. [4], which are designed to quantify the potential and exercise the voting power of delegates.

Definition 4.1 (Potential Voting Power). We measure the potential voting power of a delegate by counting how often the delegate could have changed the outcome of a proposal vote by changing their own vote. Formally, the potential power $p_{pot} \in \{0, 1\}$ of a delegate who participated in a proposal vote is defined as

$$p_d^{pot} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } v_d > \frac{1}{2}(V^{(y)} + V^{(n)}) - V^{(y)} + \delta_d v_d > 0 \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases},$$

where $V^{(y)}$ and $V^{(n)}$ are the number of Yes- and No-votes on the proposal, respectively. Furthermore, v_d denotes delegate d 's number of votes, and $\delta_d \in \{0, 1\}$ indicates whether delegate d voted Yes (1) or No (0) on the proposal.

The overall potential power of a delegate is then defined as the mean of p_d^{pot} over all proposals.

Definition 4.2 (Exercised Voting Power). The exercised voting power measures how often the vote of a delegate actually changed the out-

come of a proposal vote, i.e. how often the result would have been different without the delegate's votes. It is defined as

$$p_d^{ex} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \left(\frac{V^{(y)} - \delta_d v_d}{V^{(y)} + V^{(n)} - v_d} > \frac{1}{2} \right) \neq \left(\frac{V^{(y)}}{V^{(y)} + V^{(n)}} > \frac{1}{2} \right) \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}.$$

Again, the overall exercised power is then defined as the mean over all p_d^{ex} .

Fig. 8(a) plots the potential and exercised voting power of delegates in Compound's governance system. The chart reveals that a substantial portion of the potential voting power is shared among just four of the largest delegates. Notably, one of them could have altered the outcome of five out of the nine proposals they voted on. This observation is once again evidence of how much power lies in the hand of a select few individuals. However, we also find that these individuals do not exercise their power often; their actual voting activity falls significantly short of their potential influence.

The same is true for Uniswap (Fig. 8(b)): Large delegates only exercise their voting power rarely. This is examined in more detail in Section 5.2 when we compare how differently large and small delegates vote and find that large delegates often vote in line with small delegates.

Note that most potential and exercised voting power of small delegates that can be seen in the figures stems from two proposals with very close outcomes (which means that they could have been influenced by many delegates): Proposal 16 for Compound⁵ and Proposal 1.2 for Uniswap.⁶

5. Delegate classification and voting behavior

In this section, we investigate the voting behavior exhibited by various categories of delegates.

Section 3 hints at a difference in the structure of the ENS' delegation network. In the following, we set out to quantify this difference. To achieve this, we categorize the delegates into two distinct groups: Delegates who receive at least 50% of their voting power from a single token holder are labeled as *single holder delegates*. The remaining delegates are classified as *community delegates*.

5.1. Single holder delegates vs. community delegates

Fig. 9 shows the share of delegated tokens that is controlled by community delegates. The difference between governance systems is apparent: For ENS, about 60% of voting rights are in the hands of community delegates, while it is less than 10% for Compound and Uniswap.

⁵ <https://compound.finance/governance/proposals/16>.

⁶ <https://app.uniswap.org/#/vote/1/2>.

Fig. 8. Potential and exercised voting power of delegates.

Fig. 9. Share of delegated tokens controlled by community delegates (i.e. delegates who receive less than 50% of their votes from a single address).

While the fraction of voting rights held by community delegates has always been low for Compound, community delegates historically had more influence in the early stages of Uniswap governance.

The above observations illustrate that delegations are not utilized to a great extent in Compound and Uniswap governance. Most voting power lies in the hands of delegates who receive most of their voting power from a single token holder. It is possible that in many such cases, the two addresses are controlled by the same entity. In this regard, Compound and Uniswap governance show similarities to shareholder meetings, where large investors represent their interests. The ENS, on the other hand, is more similar to a decentralized community.

As a next step, we compare the voting behavior of community delegates and single holder delegates. We find that both groups vote similarly: They only voted differently on three Compound proposals and one Uniswap proposal. More precisely, only in these four cases did the majority of community delegates vote for a different outcome than the majority of single holder delegates.

5.2. Large vs. small delegates

In the following, we compare the voting behavior of large and small delegates. *Large delegates* are defined as the largest delegates that collectively hold at least 90% of the voting rights at the time of a proposal, while all other delegates are categorized as *small delegates*.

It is clear that large delegates, defined in this way, hold all the power in the governance system and can decide any vote in their favor. However, the critical question is how frequently they use this power to override the minority of small delegates.

Our findings show that this only rarely happens: In Compound governance, large delegates only vote differently from small ones on six out of the 84 proposals. For Uniswap, the picture is similar: Here, large and small delegates only disagree on a single proposal, and even that is a

narrow one: On proposal 1.2, large delegates are 50.5% in favor, while small delegates oppose it (34.5% are in favor).

6. Address clustering

During all the analyses, it is important to keep in mind that multiple addresses—holder as well as delegate addresses—can be controlled by the same entity. This fact can make it challenging to determine the actual distribution of power in a governance system and can lead to the illusion of greater decentralization in the system than what truly exists.

Moreover, the situations of a single entity controlling multiple addresses are actually favored by the design of the delegation rules of the governance systems: It is only possible for a token holder to delegate all of their tokens to a single address. A token holder wishing to delegate to multiple delegates must split their tokens across multiple addresses and delegate separately from these addresses.

A situation in which an entity requires multiple addresses is a large token holder with a delegation program. An example of an entity running such a program is venture capital firm a16z [25].

To identify such scenarios, we consider transfers of governance tokens between addresses. When tokens are sent from one address to another, it strongly suggests that both addresses are under the control of the same entity. Examining these transfers creates a network of addresses with links between them. From this network, we extract the connected components. Throughout the process, it is necessary to exclude certain addresses, like those associated with centralized exchanges. Using this method, we find a number of groups of addresses of Compound and Uniswap token holders that are potentially controlled by a single entity.

Fig. 10 shows two examples of such groups. It is conceivable that these addresses are part of a16z’s delegation program [25]. Of course, it is important to keep in mind that this method is not bullet-proof, and we refrain from making definitive claims about the structure of control of the addresses shown in the figure. With these examples, our goal is to illustrate that blockchain-based governance systems are not always entirely transparent, and that the power within them can be more centralized than it initially perceived.

7. Conclusion

Our analysis reveals a significant concentration of voting power in all three governance systems, with a majority controlled by a limited number of addresses. Additionally, the often low degree of participation in voting leads to even more influence of those with significant voting power who actively participate. We state these observations without judgment. Nonetheless, they do illustrate the challenges of building a truly decentralized governance systems.

In other aspects, we find noteworthy differences between Compound and Uniswap on the one side and ENS on the other side. Besides the voting power being slightly more decentralized for the latter, community

Fig. 10. Addresses possibly controlled by a single entity based on token transfers.

delegates hold much more voting power in ENS governance. In contrast, for Compound and Uniswap, almost all the voting power lies in the hands of delegates that receive the majority of their voting power from a single address. In this sense, their governance systems are similar to shareholder meetings of traditional companies, where a small number of large investors represent their interests. ENS governance, on the other hand, more resembles a decentralized community.

Notably, we find that those large and powerful delegates rarely exercise their voting power to overturn a vote. In most cases, they decide in the same way as the larger community, i.e., smaller delegates or community delegates.

As the importance of DAOs continues to rise, continuing research along the lines of this paper will become increasingly compelling. The future will present opportunities for exploring a broader array of DAO governance systems and analyzing larger numbers of proposal votes.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Robin Fritsch: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Marino Müller:** Data curation, Investigation, Visualization. **Roger Wattenhofer:** Supervision, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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